

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' LIFE SKILLS THROUGH THE STEAM APPROACH

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Abstract. *Creating conditions for the development of students' creative abilities, comprehensive personal growth, and the acquisition of essential organizational and managerial skills is one of the urgent tasks of the school education system. This plays a significant role in shaping their life skills.*

The article explores the issues of developing students' life skills based on the STEAM approach, aiming to cultivate a highly cultured, intelligent, and socially active competitive specialist.

Keywords: *law, society, community, ability, competence, skill, decision, activity, culture, activeness, citizenship, collectivity.*

Currently, the task of shaping students' active life skills is complex. Two distinct characteristic positions of modern youth stand out. The first is based on the principle of self-improvement, diligence, and dedication in the chosen field of activity. The second relies on a pseudo-principle: achieving success under any circumstances and gaining the benefits of life effortlessly.

The majority of the youth in our country strive for independence and self-assertion, which is reflected in their work, actions, and favorite activities. They seek to realize their abilities and talents, contribute to the nation and society, and find their true purpose in life.

Developing students' life skills based on the STEAM approach is one of the most important and complex areas of education, as it shapes worldviews, ideals, and principles, as well as key personal qualities necessary for a young citizen's life and activities in modern conditions.

Creating opportunities for young people to realize their potential, find a worthy place in life, and actively participate in state and public affairs, science, and culture should be a priority direction of youth policy.

Researchers such as G.B. Ergashova [2] have studied the role of innovative pedagogical technologies in the development of science and education in modern society, while L. Rajabova [4] has explored advanced methods of solving mathematical problems using the STEAM education program.

Researcher Z.M. Ashurova has provided a detailed analysis of the significance of applying STEAM technology in preschool education. The article describes the emergence of STEAM technology in education, the demand for STEAM technology in preschool education, and the modules of STEAM technology [1].

A key feature of the educational process is that, against the background of the development of the student's personality, the process of educating them as a subject of professional activity takes place. Modern society needs knowledgeable, moral, and ethical people who can make independent decisions in difficult situations. A citizen with legal culture, a sense of responsibility

for their country, knowledge of how to live in civil society and a rule-of-law state, knowledge of laws and respect for them, but also knowledge of how to create them. The comprehensive development of a competitive specialist with high legal and political culture, social activity, and patriotic civic qualities is the main goal of the educational institution's upbringing work.

The system of shaping students' life skills based on the STEAM approach ensures not only the formation of a complete specialist but also the development of citizenship, cultural values, active life position, creative self-awareness, self-management, teamwork skills, and personal qualities based on moral values.

Shaping students' life skills based on the STEAM approach should be understood as a targeted activity of teachers, staff, and parents aimed at forming a system of beliefs and personal characteristics in young people to adapt them to social life and professional activity. The content of education also includes creating conditions for the development of students' spirituality based on universal values, helping them determine themselves in life, moral, civic, and professional development, and assisting in personal self-awareness.

The goal of shaping students' life skills based on the STEAM approach is the comprehensive development of a competitive specialist with high culture, intelligence, and social activity. For this reason, the development of a set of competencies that ensure the student's ability to take responsibility, make independent decisions, exercise their rights in everyday life, participate in the development of democratic institutions, and work in a team remains relevant.

Shaping students' life skills based on the STEAM approach ensures joint decision-making, mastering new technologies, carrying out innovative activities, personal and professional self-development, and self-improvement.

Shaping students' life skills based on the STEAM approach considers the abilities of graduates and integrates science, technology, engineering, and mathematics subjects.

The use of the STEAM approach manifests itself in children's desire to acquire quality knowledge and immediately apply it in practice. If the main goal of traditional education is considered to be the teaching of knowledge and its use for thinking and creativity, the STEAM approach teaches students to combine acquired knowledge with real skills. This allows school students not only to develop certain ideas but also to apply and implement them in practice.

An active student is not only a person with a developed intellect, logical thinking, a positive attitude, and advanced personal qualities but also someone who fully realizes his potential. On the other hand, inactive students struggle with their passivity and may lack communication skills.

Conducting extracurricular activities based on the STEAM approach provides opportunities not only for education but also for developing students' interests and professionally significant personal qualities. Additionally, it contributes to making students' free time meaningful, diverse, and engaging.

The development of students' life skills based on the STEAM approach can be implemented in professional-labor, civic-legal, and cultural-spiritual directions. These three areas of education should be present in lessons, student self-governance, student community organizations, educational and upbringing activity plans, and all structural components of an educational institution.

As a result of shaping students' life skills through the STEAM approach, students should develop personal qualities such as citizenship, patriotism, internationalism, political culture, social

activity, civic engagement, teamwork, love for family, respect for human rights and freedoms, positive legal awareness, and a drive for success.

Developing students' life skills in the most important fields of education, including economics, politics, law, and psychology, encompasses the main directions of the efforts of the entire faculty during the educational process.

Introducing each class of students consistently and in detail to textbooks, educational-methodological guides, and the requirements set for students.

Providing students with all the specified materials and ensuring their availability throughout the academic year. Informing students about the skills and technologies of academic work in various subjects, summarizing the experiences of advanced and excellent students, and sharing these experiences among students; developing skills in taking notes, making conclusions, reviewing, and explaining.

- Introducing students to research and organizational skills and technologies.
- Developing self-management, self-esteem, self-discipline, and reflection abilities in individuals.
- Enhancing individual competence in decision-making and consistently and responsibly achieving personal goals.
- Developing a sense of responsibility, self-discipline, duty, and proportionality concerning oneself, one's family, other people, and the state, in connection with the necessity of comprehensively mastering a chosen field.
- Assisting students in employment, taking into account the characteristics of the economy, and integrating them into various fields of activity.

The formation of students' life skills based on the STEAM approach enables them to take responsibility, actively participate in joint decision-making, engage in various forms of social design, and resolve conflicts. These competencies can also be acquired through the activation of various forms of self-governance bodies.

Students' participation in extracurricular activities creates favorable conditions for developing their creative abilities, fostering multidimensional personal development, and acquiring necessary organizational and management skills.

The development of extracurricular educational activities in the formation of students' life skills based on the STEAM approach is carried out in the following areas:

1. Activating the activities of the administration and active students in the civic, cultural, and moral education sphere.
2. Developing and implementing targeted programs to prevent drug addiction, crime, and undesirable offenses.
3. Creating a model for providing students with information in coordination with the information service and establishing a student newspaper as a student management body.
4. Developing a system for organizing and conducting cultural, scientific, and sports events, thematic seminars, and a school for active students.
5. Developing a program for working with younger students and adapting them to the characteristics of student life.
6. Implementing state youth policy through public organizations operating within the educational institution.

Modern education should not only provide knowledge but also create conditions for shaping individuals capable of overcoming social uncertainties, making decisions, and most importantly, taking responsibility for them, as well as engaging in communication and collaboration.

Therefore, the main task of forming students' life skills based on the STEAM approach is to prepare individuals who can express themselves in the key areas of life—educational and cognitive, professional, family, spiritual and cultural, and socio-political spheres.

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